

Effect of DMF on the solvation behavior of BiBr₃ in MeOH and MeCN as a function of temperature

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Manuscript received 20 February 2002, revised 11 February 2003, accepted 16 April 2003

This paper reports the effect of addition of dimethylformamide on the conductivity and solvation behavior of bismuth bromide in methanol and acetonitrile in between 288 and 318 K. Shedlovsky model of conductivity is used to evaluate the limiting molar conductance (Λ_m^0) and association constant (K_a). The conductivity decreases whereas the solvation behavior increases in both the cases of solvents at all studied temperatures. Ion-pair formation constant (K_p), mass law constant (K_T), Walden product and thermodynamic parameters were computed. DMF appears to preferentially solvate the species of bismuth bromide. Born model of solvation has been verified.

We have studied the conductivity behavior of bismuth nitrate in water + DMF/DMSO¹. Very little work has been carried out in the field of conductivity behavior of BiBr₃ except for a small piece of work². This has prompted us to study the electrical conductivity of BiBr₃ in MeOH, MeCN, DMF and their mixtures at four different temperatures to elucidate the solvation behavior of ions under existing conditions.

Results and discussion

Limiting molar conductance :

The solutions of BiBr₃ in MeOH, MeCN, DMF and various compositions of MeOH/MeCN + DMF (v/v) were subjected to conductivity measurement at 288, 298, 308 and 318 K. The specific conductance obtained was used to determine the molar conductance. Kraus-Bray equation³ related to 1 : 1 electrolyte was used initially as BiBr₃ undergoes ionization^{1,4} in DMF in the manner $2\text{BiBr}_3 \rightleftharpoons [\text{BiBr}_2]^+ + [\text{BiBr}_4]^-$. The Kraus-Bray plot related to 1 : 1 electrolyte was drawn and from its intercept the molar conductance at infinite dilution (Λ_m^0) was obtained. This value was used to evaluate limiting molar conductance by Shedlovsky model⁵. This model gives improved value of Λ_m^0 as it accounts for the effect of ionic mobility and activity coefficient on conductivity. The Shedlovsky equation may be represented as

$$\frac{1}{S\Lambda_m} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_m^0} + \frac{C\Lambda_m S f_{\pm}^2 K_a}{\Lambda_m^0{}^2} \quad (1)$$

where,

$$S = \left[\frac{\beta\sqrt{C\Lambda_m}}{2\Lambda_m^0{}^{3/2}} + \sqrt{1 + \frac{\beta^2 C\Lambda_m}{4\Lambda_m^0{}^3}} \right]^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\log f_{\pm} = \frac{-1.8246 \times 10^6 (C\alpha)^{1/2} / (\epsilon T)^{3/2}}{1 + 50.24 \times 10^8 R(C\alpha)^{1/2} (\epsilon T)^{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{S\Lambda_m}{\Lambda_m^0} \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \frac{8.20 \times 10^5 \Lambda_m^0}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} + \frac{82.5}{\eta(\epsilon T)^{1/2}} \quad (5)$$

$$R = q = \frac{e^2}{2\epsilon kT} \quad (6)$$

and K_a is the association constant. The value of α was determined using eqn. (4). From the intercept and slope of the linear plot of $1/S\Lambda_m$ vs $C\Lambda_m S f_{\pm}^2$, the limiting conductance and the association constant (K_a) were determined. The values are shown respectively in Tables 1 and 2.

The temperature enhances the conductivity value for all compositions of MeOH/MeCN + DMF. It is due to the increase in thermal energy and mobility of ions. Magnitude of increase is larger in the beginning (0–20% DMF).

Table 1. Experimental molar conductance (Λ_m^0 , S cm² mol⁻¹) at infinite dilution for BiBr₃ from Shedlovsky model in various solvent compositions (v/v) of MeOH/MeCN + DMF at different temperatures

Temp. K	MeOH + DMF						MeCN + DMF					
	0	20	40	60	80	100	0	20	40	60	80	100% DMF
288	115	98	96	83	62	46	127	88	85	69	57	46
298	128	111	109	93	69	53	139	98	93	77	64	53
308	139	128	122	106	77	58	147	109	101	83	73	58
318	147	143	139	116	83	67	164	116	108	91	81	67

Table 2. Experimental values of K_a for BiBr₃ in various compositions of MeOH + DMF and MeCN + DMF at different temperatures

Temp. K	MeOH + DMF						MeCN + DMF					
	0	20	40	60	80	100	0	20	40	60	80	100% DMF
288	76.3	74.0	51.2	61.7	43.8	30.1	7.1	26.6	36.9	29.2	29.3	30.1
298	75.1	75.1	55.3	66.7	45.3	33.4	8.9	31.5	37.4	35.1	31.6	33.4
308	64.2	86.2	60.8	66.7	43.0	32.1	7.2	38.7	35.3	32.0	37.3	32.1
318	43.5	80.8	70.7	45.1	33.9	37.5	9.3	34.3	31.5	34.6	41.1	37.5

Table 1 reveals that the limiting molar conductance (Λ_m^0) values of BiBr₃ decreased with the increase in DMF content in both the cases. Similar behavior was reported in literature⁶. Limiting conductance varies in the order of MeCN > MeOH > DMF. This variation may be due to the difference in solvent molecular size⁷ and their respective viscosity.

When DMF is added either to MeOH or MeCN, due to non-ideality of the mixture, the density and viscosity vary. In the case of pure solvents, the measured values were compared with the literature values⁸ and they are in good agreement. When DMF is added to BiBr₃ solution, either to MeOH or MeCN, it probably abstracts some of the MeOH or MeCN molecules from the neighbourhood of the cationic species of bismuth bromide, and occupies that position. In the meantime some of the anions might have undergone solvation by this solvent molecule. Hence, the net effect on the conductivity of BiBr₃ is larger leading to decrease in conductivity (from 0 to 20% DMF). Further addition of DMF will not have such an effect. At 60% DMF, the system becomes middle region or DMF-rich region. Here, the bulky DMF molecules overweigh the small MeOH or MeCN molecules, and hence, there is a sharp decrease in conductance.

Association constant :

Association constant was obtained from the slope of the Shedlovsky plot. The values are shown in Table 2. K_a decreased with the increase in temperature at 0, 60 and 80% DMF in MeOH + DMF mixture and at 40% DMF in MeCN + DMF mixture, indicating the endothermic behavior of the system, whereas, at other compositions of DMF, in both the cases of solvent mixtures, K_a increased. K_a was found to

increase for the initial addition of DMF either to MeOH or MeCN at all temperatures. Later it decreased continuously except at 60% DMF in MeCN + DMF mixture from 288 to 308 K. In the case of MeCN + DMF mixture, there is no proper trend in variation of K_a from one composition to another. This K_a value was used to determine the change in the value of free energy of association. Fuoss-Kraus equation^{8,9} was used to prove the ion-pair formation,

$$\Lambda_m g(c) \sqrt{C} = \Lambda_m^0 / K_p^{1/2} + \Lambda_m^{0T} K_T / K_p^{1/2} [1 - \Lambda_m / \Lambda_m^0] C \quad (7)$$

Here $g(c)$ is the factor which incorporates all inter-ionic interaction terms, K_p and K_T are ion-pair and triple ion-pair formation constants and others are with usual notations. The values of K_p and K_T were determined from the plot of $\Lambda_m g(c) \sqrt{C}$ vs $[1 - \Lambda_m / \Lambda_m^0] C$. The intercept gave $\Lambda_m^0 / K_p^{1/2}$ and slope gave $\Lambda_m^{0T} K_T / K_p^{1/2}$ (since triple ion formed was small the Λ_m^{0T} was considered equivalent to Λ_m^0). The values are shown in Table 3. K_T is smaller than K_p , i.e. the amount of ion-pair formed is larger than the amount of triple ion formed. For the initial addition of DMF to MeOH or MeCN, K_p also increased enormously and so also K_T . But probably, K_p overweighed the increase in K_T and also because of the formation of ion pairs, which led to the decrease in individual ions available for conductance process and hence conductance decreased. For further addition of DMF, K_p also increased which is on expected trend but after 60% DMF, K_p decreased and so also K_T .

Thermodynamic parameters :

The energy of activation of the conducting rate process

Table 3. Experimentally determined values of K_p and K_T for BiBr₃ in MeOH/MeCN + DMF mixture at 25°*

% Comp.	K_p		K_T	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
DMF				
0	112.3	72.2	58.8	32.3
20	148.2	75.1	69.7	28.8
40	148.2	74.4	74.3	43.1
60	127.8	76.9	59.8	53.2
80	144.8	83.8	46.8	58.8
100	84.8	84.8	62.0	62.0

*(1) = MeOH + DMF mixture, (2) = MeCN + DMF mixture.

may be obtained from the Arrhenius equation⁵, $A_m^0 = Ae^{-E_a/RT}$, where A is the frequency factor, R the gas constant and others are with usual notation. From the linear plot of $\log A_m^0$ vs $1/T$, E_a , the energy of activation of the rate process, is calculated and is shown in Table 4. The value of E_a slightly increased with increase with DMF composition, which is in accordance with decrease in A_m^0 values. ΔH , the change in enthalpy, was evaluated¹¹ from the slope of the linear plot of $\log A_m^0/T$ vs $1/T$. These values are shown in Table 4. The ΔH values are positive, indicating the systems to follow endothermic behavior. ΔG , the change in free energy of association, was calculated from the equation, $\Delta G = -RT \ln K_a$. This was calculated at different temperatures, averaged out, and the values are shown in Table 4. ΔG is found to be negative, hinting the fact that endothermic behavior of the systems proposed earlier is feasible and the reaction is spontaneous. Finally, change in entropy, which

is the measure of disorderness of the system, was also computed. ΔS is very small but positive in all the cases under study. It means that the steric hinderance restricts the movement of the species in that solvent or solvent mixture.

Walden product :

Dependence of conductance on the viscosity⁵ of the medium was shown by Walden, which is the product of limiting conductance of an electrolyte and the viscosity of the solvent. The product is calculated at all temperatures and % compositions of MeOH/MeCN + DMF and are shown in Table 5. Walden product decreased sharply with the increase in temperature for pure MeOH and very marginal decrease for the next added DMF to it. But no notable effect on Walden product in the case of MeCN or MeCN + DMF was observed. The corrected Stoke's radius (r_1) is calculated for all the cases using the expression, $r_1 = 0.82Z/\Lambda_m^0 \eta_o + 0.0103 \varepsilon + r_y$, $r_y = 0.85 \text{ \AA}$ for dipolar unassociated solvents and 1.13 \AA for protic and other associated solvents. The variation in the value either with temperature or composition in both the solvent mixtures are on the expected line.

Thermodynamics of solvation :

Solvation is a process where an ion gets covered by the solvent sheath and the solvent molecules present in this sheath is called solvation number. Born equations are used to compute thermodynamic parameters of solvation, such as ΔG_{s-s} , ΔH_{s-s} and ΔS_{s-s} . Computed values are shown in Table 6 and are different from those of thermodynamics of association. The stability of the species in solution depends on the free energy change arising from solute-solvent

Table 4. Computed thermodynamic parameters for BiBr₃ under varying compositions (v/v) of MeOH + DMF and MeCN + DMF*

Parameter	0		20		40		60		80		100% DMF	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	6.7	6.3	9.5	5.8	8.3	6.2	8.1	7.2	7.6	9.6	9.2	9.2
ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	4.9	3.1	7.0	4.9	7.0	3.9	5.6	4.7	5.4	6.1	6.7	6.7
$\Delta S \times 10^{-2}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	5.1	2.7	6.0	4.5	6.0	4.5	5.4	4.3	4.9	4.9	5.1	5.1
$-\Delta G$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	10.4	5.2	11.0	8.8	10.3	8.9	10.3	8.8	9.3	8.9	8.8	8.8

*(1) = MeOH + DMF mixture, (2) = MeCN + DMF mixture.

Table 5. Walden product ($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_o$, S cm² mol⁻¹ kg m⁻¹ s⁻¹) of the conducting molecular species of BiBr₃ in MeOH + DMF and MeCN + DMF mixture*

Temp. K	0		20		40		60		80		100% DMF	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
288	0.72	0.53	0.68	0.42	0.70	0.49	0.66	0.46	0.54	0.44	0.41	0.41
298	0.70	0.51	0.65	0.42	0.67	0.47	0.64	0.44	0.50	0.44	0.39	0.39
308	0.66	0.50	0.66	0.42	0.67	0.46	0.62	0.42	0.49	0.45	0.39	0.39
318	0.61	0.53	0.66	0.42	0.66	0.45	0.63	0.43	0.48	0.46	0.40	0.40

*(1) = MeOH + DMF mixture, (2) = MeCN + DMF mixture.

Table 6. Thermodynamics of solvation for BiBr_3 in various compositions of MeOH + DMF and MeCN + DMF at different temperatures*

Temp. K	MeOH + DMF																	
	0			20			40			60			80			100% DMF		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)
288	256	0.045	269	249	0.042	261	252	0.040	264	245	0.037	256	244	0.034	254	208	0.026	215
298	254	0.050	260	245	0.046	259	249	0.045	262	243	0.041	255	237	0.037	248	204	0.028	212
308	249	0.052	265	249	0.048	264	251	0.047	266	240	0.043	254	235	0.040	247	203	0.032	213
318	242	0.054	260	248	0.054	265	250	0.053	267	243	0.049	259	234	0.045	248	207	0.037	219
	MeCN + DMF																	
288	242	0.014	246	212	0.014	216	232	0.018	237	222	0.020	228	219	0.023	225	208	0.026	215
298	236	0.014	241	211	0.015	215	226	0.018	232	219	0.021	225	218	0.025	226	204	0.025	212
308	236	0.015	240	213	0.016	218	223	0.020	230	211	0.023	218	222	0.029	231	203	0.032	213
318	244	0.016	249	212	0.017	217	222	0.021	229	216	0.025	224	224	0.033	235	207	0.037	219

*(1) = ΔG_{s-s} (kJ mol⁻¹), (2) = ΔS_{s-s} (K⁻¹ kJ mol⁻¹), (3) = ΔH_{s-s} (kJ mol⁻¹).

interaction. Larger the negative ΔG_{s-s} higher will be the stability of the species in that solution.

Experimental

Solvent dimethylformamide (DMF), methanol (MeOH) and acetonitrile (MeCN) were purified as mentioned in literature^{1,9}. Solution of BiBr_3 (Commercial) was prepared in DMF and required amount of MeOH/MeCN was then added to it so as to get known % composition (v/v) of either MeOH/MeCN. Since BiBr_3 undergoes hydrolysis to form BiOBr , conductivity study is not possible in pure water¹⁰. Conductance was measured on an Elico CM 180 conductivity meter and a dip type calibrated conductivity cell with cell constant 0.999 cm⁻¹. All the measurements were made in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.01^\circ$). The instrument was standardized as described elsewhere¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (T. N. S.) thanks U. G. C., New Delhi, for awarding a Fellowship.

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